

Toughness-dependent net-section resistance and ductility behaviour of high-strength structural steels S700 to S960

Mirco Meissner^{*,a}, Helen Bartsch^a, Markus Feldmann^a

^aRWTH Aachen University, Institute of Steel Construction, Germany
m.meissner@stb.rwth-aachen.de, h.bartsch@stb.rwth-aachen.de, feldmann@stb.rwth-aachen.de

* Corresponding author

ABSTRACT

Structural steels with higher strengths enable slender and material saving, thus particularly sustainable construction. According to the second generation of EN 1993-1-1, which is to be applied in the future, design of steel structures is already possible up to steel grade S700. However, already now, the standardization committee CEN/TC/250/SC3 has commissioned the respective WG12 to prepare rule proposals for the Eurocode for the design of steel structures using steel grades in the range S700 to S960. Clarification of the material requirements in this context is at the very beginning of the works. The question arises as to whether the set of requirements as formulated so far for steels up to S700 can continue to exist not only in the amount of minimum or limit-values, but also whether the type of requirements would then still be appropriate. This paper reports on component-scale experimental investigations on several high-strength steels S700 to S960 (HSS) with special focus on the dependence of the load-bearing behaviour and the ductility properties on the varying material toughness at different temperatures. For the lower-shelf, the results can be compared with the current design approach to avoid brittle failure according to EN 1993-1-10, while the experimental investigations also can be evaluated with regard to a possible upper-shelf toughness criterion to ensure ductile behaviour.

Keywords: high-strength steel, material requirements, ductility, net-cross-section

1 INTRODUCTION

High-strength steels enable high load-bearing capacities, large spans and resource-saving construction methods. To utilise this potential, the load-bearing capacity and reliability of structures with these steels must be accurately predicted.

For use in steel construction, steels must fulfil minimum requirements, which means that the material requirements for a design according to Eurocode3 in the ultimate limit state are ensured. The current regulations consider the yield strength ratio as well as the elongation at failure which both are characteristics of the roundbar tensile test, meaning the toughness is not considered.

This paper discusses the transition from upper shelf behaviour represented by full net-section resistance to brittle fracture with focus on the toughness and ductility of steel. Therefore, component scale tension as well as laboratory scale test were performed at different temperatures. For each temperature an evaluation of the load bearing behaviour of the component scale test with regard to the material behaviour determined by means of the laboratory scale tests can be carried out. This allows direct conclusions to be drawn about the relation between the toughness and the upper shelf behaviour as well as the ductility.

2 STATE OF THE ART AND PREVIOUS RESEARCH

2.1 Material Requirements

The verifications in the ultimate limit state (ULS) of the upper shelf go hand in hand with the basic assumption of sufficient material toughness, which is necessary to enable extensive plastifications. These requirements (*Table 1*) are specified in FprEN 1993-1-1:2022 [2] for steel grades up to S700 via the

- yield strength ratio f_u/f_y and the
- elongation at fracture A

The in the currently valid version of the EN 1993-1-1 [3] still existing criterion of uniform elongation $e_u \geq 15 - f_y/E$ was cancelled [4–6]. Furthermore, prEN 1993-1-10 [7] specifies upper shelf toughness requirements. Here the minimum energy KV_{US} should not be less than 100J in a Charpy-V-notch impact test for static loading, while seismic design requires 125J. In this case the upper shelf is defined as room temperature, which not necessarily is the case.

The question arises as to whether the current material requirements of FprEN 1993-1-1 [2] and prEN 1993-1-10 [7] can also be transferred to strength ranges up to S960 in terms of type and size.

Table 1: Ductility requirements according to FprEN 1993-1-1 [2]

	S235 – S700 (FprEN 1993-1-1 [2])	
	For plastic global analysis	For elastic global analysis
f_u/f_y	≥ 1.10	≥ 1.05
A	$\geq 15 \%$	$\geq 12 \%$

To assess the toughness behaviour of steel, a component subjected to tensile stress with a crack must be used. *Figure 1* shows the temperature dependent deformation and fracture behaviour of steel components with an indication of the fracture mechanisms. There is a temperature T_i corresponding to the ductile crack initiation, which characterises the time of the first ductile cracking processes on a microscopic level and stable crack propagation under constant energy consumption. Furthermore, from a global perspective, it becomes clear that assuming sufficiently high toughness and "small" initial defects, the material may be capable of inducing yielding or partial yielding in the net-cross-section. In most cases, crack growth is only initiated at the initial crack tip as plastification progresses. The microscopic fracture mechanisms "cleavage fracture" and "shear fracture" can to a certain extent be assigned to the macroscopic behaviours "brittle fracture" and "ductile fracture", whereby the latter can also occur without deformation, phenomenologically brittle, so to speak.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the temperature dependent deformation and fracture behaviour of steel components with indication of the fracture mechanisms [1]

2.2 Previous research

The following investigations focus on the upper shelf load bearing capacity of structural steel. The basis of this research is the tension resistance verification according to FprEN 1993-1-1 [2], which takes into account the yield strength f_y and the tensile strength f_u combined with the cross-section, Eq. (1), while the lower value is decisive.

$$N_{t,Rd} = \begin{cases} \frac{A \cdot f_y}{\gamma_{M0}} \\ \frac{k \cdot A_{net} \cdot f_u}{\gamma_{M2}} \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

where:

- A Gross-cross-section
- A_{net} Net-cross-section
- $k = 0.9$ Factor for sections with smooth holes (i.e. holes without notches)
- $k = 1.0$ Factor for sections with rough holes (i.e. holes with notches) or structures subjected to fatigue

Previous studies have focussed on the influence of notch size across different steel grades at room temperature [4–6]. Both, centre holed tension specimens (CHT; $k=1.0$) and centre notched tension specimens (CNT; $k=0.9$) were analysed. The results are displayed in *Figure 2*, where small d/W or $2a/W$ values correspond to small holes or notches. It can be seen, that due to the lower yield strength-ratio the EN 1993 limit values considering $f_y \cdot A_{net}$, indicated with the dotted line, increase above the $0.9 \cdot f_u \cdot A_{net}$ limit (permanent line) for higher steel grades. The grey area indicates the decisive minimum value of $N_{t,Rd}$ for the CNT specimens. For the CHT specimens, almost the full net-section resistance of $1.0 \cdot f_u \cdot A_{net}$ can be reached, while the CNT specimens fulfil the normative limit value of $0.9 \cdot f_u \cdot A_{net}$ for all notch sizes.

Figure 2: Ultimate loads of net-section specimens in comparison with EN 1993 requirements (CHT = centre holed tension, CNT = centre notched tension) [4, 6]

These results are valid for steels with enough toughness at the investigated temperature to provide upper shelf-like behaviour. To guarantee this upper shelf behaviour, temperature dependent investigations with respect to material investigations are needed, to determine the toughness dependency for various yield strength.

Based on the experimental results, full numerical calibrated damage mechanic material models were used to extend the scope of results with parametric studies. With these numerical material models an investigation of different upper shelf toughnesses for various yield strength could be performed.

In *Figure 3* the results of the parametric study are displayed. It can be seen that the needed material toughness to reach $f_y \cdot A_{net}$ or $0.9 \cdot f_u \cdot A_{net}$ depends on the yield strength ratio which is strongly dependent on the yield strength. For HSS the needed toughness to provide resistance of $0.9 \cdot f_u \cdot A_{net}$ is lower than for mild steels, while the requirement to reach $f_y \cdot A_{net}$ increases for low yield strength ratios due to a higher calculatable resistance compared to $0.9 \cdot f_u \cdot A_{net}$.

Figure 3: Upper shelf toughness requirements for net-section yielding and net section resistance for perforated cross sections with initial crack under tension (CNT) [4]

3 INVESTIGATED HIGH-STRENGTH STEEL

3.1 General

In order to obtain a comprehensive and generally valid statement about the toughness dependent load-bearing behaviour, four different steels were experimentally examined. This includes different manufacturing methods such as thermomechanical rolled steels (M) as well as quenched and tempered steels (Q and QL). Furthermore, different plate thicknesses in the range from 20mm to 61mm were investigated, for which a variation of the specimen geometry in form of the crack width was also taken into account.

3.2 Material properties

To identify the material properties of the given materials, small scale tests were carried out. This includes roundbar tensile tests as well as Charpy-V tests. The results are shown in *Figure 4* and evaluated in *Table 2*. For the roundbar tensile tests a difference between thermomechanically treated and quenched steels can be noticed. The yield strength ratio $R_m/R_{p0.2}$ for the S700M being far lower than for the quenched steels while showing a higher elongation after reaching the maximum stress. The quenched steels show higher hardening effects before reaching maximum stress with lower elongation afterwards. The reason for the lower elongation is the correlation between the necking behaviour and the toughness of the material, where the elongation after maximum stress and necking grows with increasing toughness [8].

The results of the Charpy-V tests differ tremendously between the different materials. While the S700M has a very low transition temperature reaching full upper shelf toughness of $KV_{US}=259J$ at -60 °C the investigated S960Q steels reach upper shelf behaviour only at around 20 °C to 150 °C. Meanwhile the S960Q $t=61mm$ and the S960Q $t=40mm$ show similar low temperature behaviour, starting to differ from 0 °C upwards. The graph shows, that especially the S960Q $t=61mm$ does not reach full upper shelf behaviour at an assumed room temperature of 20 °C. Nevertheless the given results of all presented steels fulfil the $T_{301,req}/T_{401,req}$ requirements of EN 10025 [9].

Figure 4: a) Technical stress-strain curves b) Temperature dependent toughness of the investigated materials

Table 2: Mechanical-technological properties of the investigated materials

Material	$R_{p0.2}$ [MPa]	R_m [MPa]	$R_m/R_{p0.2}$ [-]	A [-]	T_{30J} [°C]	T_{40J} [°C]	$T_{30J,req}/T_{40J,req}$ [°C]
S960Q t=61mm	999.5	1072.5	1.073	17.2	-40	-	-20
S960Q t=40mm	982.5	1045	1.064	15.9	-37	-	-20
S960QL t=20mm	1076	1098	1.020	16.2	-86	-	-40
S700M t=20mm	907	913	1.007	18.1	-	-127	-20

4 COMPONENT SCALE LOAD BEARING TESTS

4.1 Specimens and measurement technique

To analyse the component scale toughness dependent load bearing capacity, 22 centre notched tension specimens (CNT) were investigated, *Figure 5*. A centric waterjet cut was made in the specimens which formed the basis for a fatigue crack introduced by cyclic loading. After the cyclic loading, the notch in the centre of the plate had a width $2a$ between 10% to 30% of the plate width $W=200\text{mm}$ ($2a/W = 0.1$ to 0.3). An overview of the net-section dimension of each specimen can be taken from *Table 3*.

Figure 5: Dimensions of the centre notched tension specimens (CNT)

For each series four to five specimens at temperatures between room temperature and -120°C were investigated. For the low temperature tests the measuring area was boxed in a climate chamber and liquid nitrogen was introduced through cooling plates at the sides of the specimens, *Figure 6*.

Table 3: Overview of net-section dimension of the specimens

Material	S960Q t=61mm				S960Q t=40mm				S960QL t=20mm				
	RT	0	-30	-120	RT	0	-30	-120	RT	-30	-80	-100	-120
2a [mm]	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	20	20	20	20	20
W [mm]	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200
2a/W [-]	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1

Material	S700M t=20mm									
	RT	-30	-80	-120	-120	RT	-30	-120	-120	-120
2a [mm]	20	20	20	20	20	40	40	40	40	40
W [mm]	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200
2a/W [-]	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2

Tests have been carried out as quasi-static tension tests and the load has been applied displacement controlled with a speed of $0.5\text{mm}/\text{min}$, while the test specimens were clamped at both ends. The applied force and the displacement of the piston have been measured during the tests as well as the temperature at three points on the specimen surface (T1-T3). Displacement transducers (DT) over a length of 240mm and strain gauges (SG) have been used to gain a deeper understanding of the specimen behaviour in the area of the notch, *Figure 7*.

Figure 6: Specimen S960Q t=40mm in the cooling chamber after the -120°C test

Figure 7: Arrangement of measuring sensors a) Front b) Back

4.2 Results

Figure 8 a) displays the stress in relation to the strain according to the displacement transducer for the CNT specimens of the S960Q t=40mm for the investigated temperatures. For temperatures above 0°C , the full net-section resistance is reached, while the ductility shrinks tremendously due to the decreased temperature. In addition, a transition from mainly “shear failure” to “cleavage failure” can be observed when looking at the microscopic fracture mechanism. The specimens tested at -30°C and -120°C show pure brittle fracture in the linear elastic range. The reduction of the load bearing capacity

due to the lower temperatures and respectively the lower toughness can be analysed in *Figure 8 b*). The transition behaviour can be seen as similar compared to the toughness transition behaviour. Besides the actual lower maximum stress, the fracture surfaces show significant differences. While the specimen at room temperature fractured after forming shear lips (*Figure 9 a*) the fracture surface of the -120 °C specimen show pure brittle failure mode, *Figure 9 b*). In addition, the water jet cut and the fatigue crack of the CNT specimens can be recognised.

Figure 8: CNT specimens of the S960Q t=40mm (2a/W=0.3) at different temperatures a) Stress in relation to the strain according to the displacement transducer b) Evaluation of the maximum stress in terms of the factor k

Figure 9: Fracture of the CNT specimen of the S960Q t=40mm at a) Room temperature b) -120°C

Similar transition curves can be calculated for the other investigated materials. For the S960Q t=61mm (*Figure 10 a*) a significantly lower maximum stress at -30°C compared to the S960Q t=40mm can be evaluated, while both materials show full load bearing capacity at 0 °C. The S960QL t=20mm shows enlarged resistance up to a temperature of -80°C due to the increase of yield strength for declining temperatures (*Figure 11*) [1, 10, 11]. while the toughness does not shrink below a critical value to trigger macroscopic brittle fracture. Below -80°C a decrease in load bearing capacity can be noted with brittle fracture being the leading failure mode, *Figure 10 b*).

Figure 10: Evaluation of the maximum stress of the CNT specimens at different temperatures in terms of the factor k
a) S960Q $t=61\text{mm}$ ($2a/W=0.3$) b) S960QL $t=20\text{mm}$ ($2a/W=0.1$)

Looking at the results of the CNT specimens of the S700M $t=20\text{mm}$ the high, low temperature toughness can be recognised. The load bearing capacity grows steadily with decreasing temperatures, whereby at a temperature of -120°C the normative upper shelf limit value of $0.9 \cdot f_u \cdot A_{\text{net}}$ is still complied with, Figure 12. Evaluating the analysed load bearing behaviour with regard to the determined toughness of the individual materials a trend can be recognised. For all specimens tested at a temperature with an associated toughness of at least 60J , full load-bearing capacity in terms of $0.9 \cdot f_u \cdot A_{\text{net}}$ can be determined (For the S960QL $t=20\text{mm}$ even 40J was sufficient). These experimental results confirm the numerical results given in previous research based on damage mechanic models, where the minimum toughness to provide full load bearing capacity according to the verification model of EN 1993-1-1 [2] of 60J for S700 steel grades, 40J for S960 steel grades was determined [4, 5].

Figure 11: Influence of temperature on the fracture inducing stress[1]

Figure 12: Evaluation of the maximum stress of the CNT specimens at different temperatures in terms of the factor k
a) S700M t=20mm (2a/W=0.1) b) S700M t=20mm (2a/W=0.2)

5 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

In this paper the toughness dependency of net-section resistance of HSS (S700-S960) was experimentally analysed and evaluated. Four different steels including thermomechanically treated and quenched steels with different plate thicknesses between 20mm and 61mm with different temperature dependent transition behaviour in the sense of toughness were investigated. The experimental investigations revealed, that a toughness of 60J is sufficient to provide full net-section yielding resistance for tensile loading of HSS (S700-S960) according to EN 1993-1-1. This confirms previous numerical investigations based on damage mechanic approaches in terms of values as well as the fact that the requirements for toughness decrease with increasing yield strength.

To provide a comprehensive verification of the given results, further geometries such as longitudinal and transverse attachments with different crack configurations will be investigated. Furthermore, other correlations of the mechanical-technological properties and the load bearing behaviour will be evaluated as well as numerical recalculations based on damage mechanic approaches will be carried out.

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